

WE ALL BLEED FOR THE SAME JUSTICE

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Manuscript ID: ALRJ-V1111-A3-007

Publication Date: September 3, 2022

Journal Series: Volume 1 – Issue 1

ABSTRACT

The ongoing racial disparities in employment, housing, and many other spheres of society have reignited discussion about the potential impact of prejudice. Although discrimination is less obvious today than it was in the pre-civil rights era, when it was overt and pervasive, this presents challenges for social science conceptualization. Interest in the potential impact of discrimination has increased in light of the persistence of racial inequalities in employment, housing, and other spheres of society.

However, modern forms of prejudice are frequently subtle and covert, which makes them difficult to conceptualize from a social science perspective. Although racial discrimination at work, at home, financing, and in market interactions was the emphasis of this article, (such as education, health care, and the criminal justice system) including other forms of prejudice (example: gender, age, sexual orientation).

India's massive social, religious, political, and economic system of social hierarchy is known as the caste system. Discussions on its genesis would be tiresome since, in part because of its tight ties to Hindu ceremonial practices and the fabric of Hinduism, it continues to be contentious. The Manusmiriti's documentation, on the other hand, makes it clear that the system dates back to 1250 BC. Four basic castes, or "varnas," make up the social structure, which is important to comprehend (groups). The order of importance is as follows: Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas, Shudras, and Dalits.

In today's time, people still believe in the four groups of the caste system. As they see people firstly by their origin (place of birth and caste). It has been observed that the Dalit and the backward class people are facing issues while

sharing common essentials in society. In the early period, it was also noted that the Dalit people were denied to go to religious places such as temples, and it was seen that the Brahmins have the first hand with it. Since discrimination is not recently started as it was rooted in ancient times. It has been observed that we have a patriarchal society from the ruler's era. Even if the king is not capable of the post still he gets the throne of the kingdom. In India, people mostly look to the background of an individual, not the qualities and capabilities of the person. In society, people must look at an individual by his work, not by his caste, race, gender, religion, and place of birth.

INTRODUCTION

Discrimination is one of the hugely controversial topics in today's world. Racial discrimination is defined as the unfair treatment of individuals or groups based on their race or ethnicity. Individuals receive differential treatment when they are given different treatments based on their race. Discrimination is in the form of internal and external in society. People face discrimination regarding employment (in their workplace), children face problems in their school and colleges, and women face inequality regarding jobs and their gender which gives the feeling of being left back in society.

Discrimination is defined as the denial of opportunities or equal rights to a certain group of people who may be distinguished by factors like their gender, race, or religion. Since we have records, the society in which we live has struggled with this delicate issue. In our world, discrimination has always been a problem. It is one of the topics that has generated the most discussion both now and throughout history. Every country likely practices at least one sort of discrimination against different groups of people. Denial of chances or equal

rights to a particular group of people who may be differentiated by factors like their gender, colour, or religion is known as discrimination. The world we live in has been battling with this complex issue since the dawn of time; as far back as we have records. Gender is also one of the issues where there is a huge comparison between men and women in the country.

Discrimination is still practiced today as well as in the past.

For example, students are subjected to prejudice based on their colour, caste, sex, religion, and place of birth in schools. It has been observed that students from upper classes are given more possibilities than students from lower classes.

- In contrast, discrimination also occurs in politics, marriages, households, companies, and temples.
- The caste group that was able to acquire education under the previous system has done exceptionally well in getting modern education. Groups that were denied access to education or were forbidden from receiving it have inevitably fallen behind.
- While still being intimately related to economic standing, "upper caste" is disproportionately prevalent among the urban middle classes in our society.

DISCRIMINATION IN SECTORS

Discrimination and oppression in sectors are present in the earlier and modern eras. The amount of oppression and discrimination has been low, but it is still present in society. Discrimination had been observed in many sectors like employment, education, gender, marriage, temples, and so on. In India, people

are not treated equally regarding job perspectives. As it has been heard and seen that upper-class people get high reputation jobs with good salaries whereas the backward-class people struggle a lot to get a good job. People from various religions and castes apply for good jobs for a good standard of living, but unfortunately because of unequal treatment in society people face lots of problems.

It has been observed that a common man who is from a backward class face lot of problem compared to an upper class. It has also been observed that the power of money also plays a huge role in the employment sector. It has been considered that if a man has a good amount of money he can get a stable job whereas the backward class worker has to struggle to get a good job and a peaceful life. In the employment sector, it has also been observed that men get the first preference when selecting a job as compared to women. Sometimes there is a huge difference in the wages compared to men and women. In this sector, we can see the biasedness regarding gender.

Where it has also been observed in rural areas that girls are denied access to education because of the orthodox thinking of parents and society as they believe there is no use for education for girls. They consider that the girl's education is not important as they had to do household chores. Society thinks that girls and women should only work in the home and look after the family. Rural people don't consider women as an important aspect of society. People gave more importance to men as compared to women in society. They believe that the technical work is mainly done by men.

Regarding marriages, there is a huge conflict as it has been mandated that the same caste people should marry each other. There is no acceptance of love marriage in society. In society, it has been believed that the same caste and the same religion marriage should happen. Society doesn't accept marriage with the

other caste. Marriage creates huge conflict issues in society as well as in families.

Regarding temples, it has been observed in the past that the Dalit people and backward class people were denied to enter into the temples as they consider impure. Whereas the temple is considered the holy place where all are the children of gods no one should be prohibited to enter the temple, but the society in past makes illogical rules regarding the temples. Brahmins believed that the Bhramins have major access to the temples.

Looking at all the sectors we can say that because of the oppression, and discrimination there is no harmony or fraternity left in society. Because of discrimination many people lost opportunities, committed suicide, and had been suffered from mental issues.

ROHIT VEMULA CASE

Many of you might know this case as it has been one of the life-changing incidents of a Dalit student, named Rohit Vemula, who committed suicide. He was a student studying at Hyderabad University. The university decided to suspend five Dalit students and expel them from the hostel. In college, he suffered high discrimination regarding his caste and religion.

The university did not behave properly with the students as they were neglected and corned in the university and the hostel. He committed suicide because of this caste discrimination in his college as he suffered a lot of humiliation and oppression. He shared his views by posting a video on social media in which he talk about his thoughts regarding the matter he was facing in the university as well as the feeling of loneliness.

From this case, we can see that discrimination can be very harmful to an individual. Discrimination can cause emotional damage to the person and he can commit suicide. People just spell the words and later they forget but the words can cause actual damage to the person. Rohit Vemula was not the one person who face discrimination and die many people faced various types of oppression in today's world.

CONCLUSION

From the article, we can conclude that Article 15 of the Constitution of India state that there should be no discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex, and place of birth. As we can say that article 15 supports people from facing oppression and discrimination, but they contradict many aspects where people are treated unequally and still faces discrimination. In the rural area, there is no awareness related to justice, equal treatment, and rights for the people, whereas people face lots of humiliation in the society.

As we can say that Rohit Vemula died on 17th January 2016. Even after Article 15 was imposed there was suicide committed because of the discriminatory way of the university and the humiliation that he faced. Hence we can say that even though the article is enforced but still people face discrimination on the bases of race, caste, sex, and religion. My article gives a glimpse that there is still discrimination and oppression in society. Even though the law exists it contradicts society.